

THE VAIN SACRIFICE OF DALIT PATRIOTS: ONE ACT PLAY

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Introduction

Though British were also the enemies to untouchables, they were not directly involved in oppressing the untouchables. As such, Ambedkar feels that the broken men or untouchable classes have to wage struggle against the Hindu Varna System, but not against Government. The higher cast occupied front row in struggle for political right because they had enjoyed privilege in social order until the transmission of power from higher caste to British. Ambedkar and Pule strove a lot for casteless Indian society. Even in Indian post-independent scenario, the atrocities on Dalits remain almost the same. The constitutional commitment of the postcolonial India is to establish equality and social justice, but the age old social structure of India is unable to succeed in establishing the social justice. Social and economic inequality still pervades at the core of Indian reality. The National Crime Records Bureau of India reports: “Every hour — two Dalits are assaulted; every day — three Dalit women are raped, two Dalits are murdered and two Dalit houses are burnt.” The ironical situation in India is that untouchability was banned by Indian constitution long back, but majority of Dalits face caste discrimination in rural India. They do not have access to communal water sources, and temples even today. If the situation of Dalits is worse in post-independence, I thought of how the situation of Dalits in pre-independent India was, and how the sacrifice of Dalits in freedom struggle was exploited.

Note: Keeping the above general notion in view, I've created fictional plot, area, and characters. The characters in the play don't aim at either any individual or any nation or any mythology.

Foreword

In nineteen thirties and forties the struggle of Hindians (a fictitious British colony) for freedom was at its zeniths, and the hearts of Hindians were wreathed with overwhelming patriotism. People from all social stratum surged forward with one rigid aim – to get freedom from the brutal rule of the British. This was the time when normal people were ready to give up their valuable lives for the sake of the right cause i.e. freedom. With the inspiration ignited by so called sublime freedom fighters, many Dalits (Broken Men) in remote villages got inspired and became the staunch followers of the leaders of freedom fighters. But the Dalits' sacrifice and martyrdom was exploited by the native-pseudo-freedom fighters to their advantage. As such no Dalit freedom fighter has been remembered even today. Dalits fought in dual way. On the one hand, Dalits fought for the freedom from British, and on the other hand, Dalits fought for emancipation from the age old Varna System.

Characters:

1. Lavya
2. Karna
3. Suodan
4. Krishnaji
5. Dharma

6. Bheem
7. Arjun
8. Nakul
9. Saha
10. Narasimha
11. Kristee
12. Peter

The Vain Sacrifice of Dalit Patriots

Act I

(The plot takes place at the outskirts of a remote village called Hariwada in Hindia, a British colony. The scene takes place before Ramalayam, a temple of God Rama. A group of higher caste led by Arjun, a kshatriya, sits on the pedestal near the temple, and another group of Dalits with half naked bodies led by LavyaMadig, a brave Dalit with beefy body, sits on the ground a little away from the other group. The groups sit in opposite directions. The both groups are eagerly waiting for the arrival of Krishnajiji, a national freedom fighter hails from Vysya higher caste. The flame of freedom fight penetrated even into the remote corners of the nation under the leadership of Krishnajiji. As there are many conflicts between the two groups, they expect the intervention of Krishnajiji to solve the conflicts between them. Both groups admire Krishnajiji as a sublime freedom fighter. As they huddle up in dejected mood expecting the arrival of Krishnajiji from a long time, a Dalit, Suodan, enters hazily and stands amidst the two groups.)

Suodan: *(barges into the two groups and pants for a moment. He's clad in soiled dress):* Krishnaji. . . (pants) Ha. .haaa. . .mm m m. . .

Arjun: *(gets up all of sudden from the pedestal, and comes adjusting his khaddar dhoti, to Suodan):* Hey! Untouchable! Why are you panting? Is there any news? What about? Is it news about Krishnaji?

Suodan: *(panting):* He. . .He. . . .

Lavya: *(clad in muddy kahdi dhoti and kurtha, Lavya clasps the hand of Suodan):* What happened to Krishnaji? Is there any danger to him?

Suodan: *(fearfully hugs Lavya):* I went to the outskirts to see Krishnaji before none of this village. There I saw Kristee, the British man who constructed a clay church amidst our Dalit Street. He had a gun in his hand. He frowned at me. I was afraid. I ran here as quickly as I can. *(Lavya takes Suodan aside to console him)*

Arjun: *(sarcastically):* Fear is the disposition and natural instinct of untouchables. The fear is streaming fast in the veins of Dalit. Dalits are all cowards. . . How can they fight for freedom?

Saha: *(clad in bright kadhi dhoti and kurtha):* Ha. . ha. .haahahaha. . . My brother, Arjun! You have rightly said. They're born to suffer, not to rebel. Don't call them Dalits! Call them Harijans.

Arjun: *(laughs):* Yes! True! Saha! You have rightly called them Harijans. The name was given to them by our leader Krishnaji. . .

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Saha: Arjun! I don't know why we called them Harijans. Can you please reveal the meaning?

Arjun: I also don't know the meaning of Harijans. To my understanding, I interpret it that Harijans are the children of God.

Saha: (*inquisitively*): Don't they have their biological fathers?

Arjun: Maybe! Their father is God Hari/Vishnu.

Saha: If so, I didn't see God Hari/Vishnu in their huts. How did they born?

Arjun: Saha! Fool! They're irrational like animals.

Saha: Animals? No. . . Worse than animals. . .

Arjun: Why?

Saha: Because we worship animals. Are they better than 'Gomaatha' the cow we worship?

Arjun: If it is so. . . they're worse than animals. . . (*Sarcastic laugh*)

(As they talk, Lavya takes Suodan to Ramalayam to pray Rama to console Suodan. Arjun and Saha looked at Lavya who try to enter the temple).

Saha: (*roars*): O God! O God! It is a great sin. Look at Lavya! Untouchable! Lavya is trying to enter the pious temple. This pious Ramalayam will be impious if he enters. (*cries loudly*) My siblings, birds of a same feather! Stop the untouchable from his heinous attempt!

(Arjun, Saha, and group surge forward to Lavya. The group of Lavya huddled up, as they feel the attempt of Lavya is a sin)

Arjun: (*Arjun barged through the crowd towards Lavya*): Ye! Untouchables! How dare you to enter the pious temple? It is a sin.

Lavya: (*widens his shaggy bosom aggressively*): Sin! What? To pray God?

Saha: (*intervenes*): Yes! Entering the pious temple . . . is sin. You're untouchables. . .

Lavya: If we are untouchables, this temple of Rama is also untouchable. . .

Arjun: (*surprisingly*): How can it be? Is abode of God untouchable? Is our pious temple untouchable? Lavya! Stop this blasphemy?

Lavya: (*looks passively at the half-naked Dalits*): Ye! Look at the emaciated people! They're the responsible for the construction of this lavish temple. Each and every stone arranged in the wall is drenched first in their sweat. Even the idol of Rama is carved out by the hands of these untouchables. Is Lord Rama untouchable, then?

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Saha: (*boastfully*): Our priests did the remedial rituals and *pujas* in opening ceremony of the temple. Their *pujas* made this temple pure and absolved from that blame.

Lavya: Ye fool! You have been drying your dirty bottom at the dirty ditch of obsolete rituals. Heed. . .

Arjun: What to heed?

Lavya: You have the opportunity to re-purify yourselves in the guise of *pujas*. I beg you to purify Dalits also. Then every individual will be equal to you. There would be no caste discrimination at all.

Saha: How is it possible? How can a slave be equal to a master?

Lavya: Heed! You would never do *puja* to purify Dalits because you need slaves. You're the self-centered human beasts. We were made untouchables by the merciless Hindu rituals, but you made yourselves untouchables.

Arjun: (*perplexingly*): Untouchables! We? How?

Lavya: It is vice versa, when you don't touch the untouchables, they also don't touch you. Therefore, you made yourselves untouchables.

Saha: Stop! Your filthy. . . Nonsense. . .

Lavya: You're untouchables . . . second-by-second. . .

Arjun: (*speaks irritatingly with widened eyes*): Mm m . . . What? Second-by-second?

Lavya: The nature made you untouchables . . . The wind that touched me touches you. Hence, you're made untouchables? Aren't you? How can you make yourselves pure every second?

Saha: (*exaggeration*): Nature? Nature also supports us as lords over Dalits.

Arjun: Yes! The geographical location of this village, Hariwada, seems to be supporting the disparity between the higher and lower strata of its inhabitants. There is a small hill like a barrier between our colony and the Dalits colony. The nature has chosen the people of higher caste to live at the east where the sun shines first on our houses. Later, it falls on Dalit colony in the west. The earth of the village is sloppy. We are chosen to live at the higher end of the ground, and the Dalits at the lower end of the sloppy ground. The rivulet flows from east to west permitting us to use the water first.

Saha: Rightly said. . . *Ha hahahah*. . .

Arjun: We wash our buffaloes and bottoms first in the rivulet that floats with contaminated water beside the Dalit colony. Then. . . the Dalits drink the adulterated water.

(*Suodan recovers from his fear and bewilderment, and stands firmly beside Lavya.*)

Suodan: Ye Fools! Do you know whom you're talking to? Provoking Lavya is as similar as provoking a wrathful tiger. Lavya is iron hearted.

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Saha: (*sarcastically*): Iron hearted . . .? Further. . .

Suodan: (*seriously*): Lavya is the true leader of his clan. He protected us from many dangers. He fought many battles in favor of his clan. He's a great wrestler. He won many wrestling competition. He had five heads as his war price. He cut the heads of five foes in battles. Those heads are hung in front of his door. He paid heed to the call of non-violence of Krishnaji and stopped violence. Otherwise, it would have been a different story. Your heads would have been . . . and he would have peeled off your skin.

Arjun: (*looks seriously at Lavya and Suodan*): Suodan! Stop your stray barking. We don't afraid of the animals. You're the slaves forever. There would be no emancipation for you. Remember the history how your ancestors starved. History reveals that you're hopeless, powerless like pigs. We molested your women, exploited your liberty. It will continue forever. The land is ours and labor is yours. We have social and economic power.

Lavya: (*philosophically*): Power is like a gyre. You may be powerful today. But we expected a ray of hope in the promising message of our great freedom fighter, Krishnaji. After independence . . . after independence . . . his slogan 'untouchability is crime' will redeem us from this hopeless situation.

Saha: (*murmurs at the ear of Arjun*): These gullible untouchables are unable to understand that who for this freedom struggle is. They're in the false notion. They don't know that this freedom fight is not for the emancipation of untouchables, but to free the landlords and higher castes from the British rule.

Lavya: What are you murmuring about?

Arjun: Nothing. . . nothing. . .

Saha: Let me tell about the contribution of Arjun in the freedom fight.

Arjun: (*Arjun looks perplexingly confusingly at Saha, and murmurs at the ear of Saha*): You know pretty well that my contribution is nothing to the freedom fight. Why are you exaggerating?

Saha: (*whispers at the ear of Arjun*): Let us not be inferior to the untouchables.

Arjun: Okay!

Saha: Arjun is the true and staunch follower of Krishnaji. He met Krishnaji many times. He fought against the British. He educated the higher castes towards the dire need of freedom. He ignited and patriotic fervor in the minds of higher castes. . .

Suodan: (*intervenes*): Lavya foiled the attempt of British to establish Church, and British school. You know?

Arjun: Why?

Suodan: Because of the Non-cooperation, and Civil Disobedience call given by Krishnaji. He rebelled against the British and chased them from our Dalit colony. Though British threatened him with their guns, he showed his bosom to the British. Lavya fulminated them . . . He's the leader of Dalit clan. He led the team towards the freedom struggle.

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Saha: (*nudges Arjun, giggles, and murmurs*): Hey! Arjun! In the past, education was not extended to Dalits, but the British tried. Krishnaji's hoax of civil disobedience has foiled the attempt of the British. . .

Arjun: *Ha .ha. .* These untouchables are emotionally strong, but intellectually weak. They're caught in the trap of civil disobedience. . .

Suodan: What are you murmuring about?

Arjun: Nothing. . .

Saha: Nothing. . . We are appreciating the effort of your freedom struggle by foiling the attempt of British to establish churches, and educational institutions in your colony.

(As the two groups are gloomily snoozing due to long waiting for the arrival of Krishnajiji, a half-naked Karna runs to the midst of the two groups. Karna is born to an unknown madwoman. He's as powerful as Arjun. People believe that God has impregnated the madwoman).

Karna: (*seriously*): Hey! Why are you snoozing like sheep? Can't you wait for Krishnaji enthusiastically? Get up! Be cheerful!

Arjun: Why do you babble, fatherless untouchable, Karna? We look after everything here.

Saha: (*pun*): He's doubly untouchable, born to untouchable mother as a fatherless son and chosen to live with untouchables. . .

Arjun: He's like eunuch . . . orphan. . .

Suodan: (*leaps a little*): Stop! Stop the humiliation. . . He's not an orphan! He's like my brother. . .

Saha: (*wittily*): Brother! Is your father his father?

Lavya: Don't provoke us. We have come here to unite under the leadership of Krishnaji. He gave a call to combined fight for the freedom. Let Krishnaji come! Let us heed his words. . . (*sonorously*) Till then, I beseech you to be calm and patient!

Arjun: To fight along with untouchables is sin. . . Why Krishnaji has given a call to fight against the British that includes the untouchables also. . .?

Saha: Krishnaji might have his own strategy . . . humbug. . .

(Nakul runs very fast amidst the two groups as if he has brought some important announcement. He comes and pants for a moment. All the people look at him with anxiety).

Arjun: (*hazily*): Nakul! My Brother! What happened?

Saha: My brother! What happened?

Razole Prabhakar / The Vain Sacrifice Of Dalit Patriots: One Act Play

Nakul: don't confuse me. . . Let me take full breath . . . let us go little way from these untouchables. . . *(They go little away from Lavya, Suodan, and Karna)*

Arjun: Did any of the untouchable dog hounded you?

Saha: Is it? Are you chased by the untouchables?

Arjun: Nakul, and Saha! You're very clever . . . you can guess what is going to happen . . . Saha! Can you prophesy what might have happened to Nakul?

Nakul: *(calm voice)*: Hey! Brothers! Don't be bemused. . . Nothing happened to me. . . I've brought message to you. . .

Arjun: *(surprise)*: Message?

Nakul: Yes. Krishnaji is about to enter the village. Dharma, and Bheem are accompanying Krishnaji. Krishnaji, our higher caste freedom fighter, has ordered me, 'Arjun, and Saha must receive me first. . . Not the foul untouchables'.

(Arjun, Nakul, and Saha go to the right corner of the stage where from Krishnajiji enters. While all the untouchables, Lavya, Karna, and Suodan look perplexedly at them, Krishnajiji enters with a wand-like staff in his hand. Krishnajiji is recognized as a great freedom fighter who propounded Quit Hindia, Civil Disobedience, Non cooperation so on and so forth).

Nakul: *(garlands and showers petals of roses on the head of Krishnajiji)*: Long live Krishnaji. . . long live Krishnaji. . .

Arjun: Krishnaji. . . Freedom fighter par excellence. . . Krishnaji is the nightmare to the British. . . He's our rescuer from bondage of the White. . . Praise the contribution of Krishnaji. . . our National Freedom Fighter. . .

(Dharma, Bheem, Arjun, Nakul, Saha, and other all higher caste people gathered around Karishna creating a lot of fuss. As the din is on, Krishnajiji looks at the group of untouchables led by Lavya).

Krishnaji: Stop! Stop the hubbub! *(the din pacifies. Krishnajiji looks mercifully at Lavya and his group, and wags his head as a token of invitation)*. Friends, give passage to Harijans. Let them come to me. . . *(Lavya and his group come to Krishnajiji. Lavya and his fellows bow down before feet of Krishnajiji seeking blessings. Krishnajiji hugs Lavya uninterestingly)*.

Lavya: *Jai Bolo. . . Krishnajiki. . . (pause) Jai Bolo . . . Krishnajiki. . . (the entire Dalit group shouts 'Jai' after Lavya)*

Krishnaji: *(whispers at the ear of Arjun)*: What is this Harijan's name?

Arjun: *(with low voice)*: Lavya.

Krishnaji: *(murmurs)*: Keep yourselves away from this dirty Harijans! Let me go and chat with them for a while. . .

Razole Prabhakar / The Vain Sacrifice Of Dalit Patriots: One Act Play

Arjun: Okay! Master. . .

Krishnaji: (*keeping his hand on the shoulder of Lavya*): I could recognize you, Harijan strong man. I think your name is Lavya who met me long back. . . Isn't it?

Lavya: (*politely*): Yes! Master?

Krishnaji: Fight for our Swaraj. . . Sacrifice for Swaraj. . . Non-Violence, and Civil Disobedience is our weapon . . .

Suodan: Krishnaji. . . ! Lavya is the staunch supporter of your foot prints. He united all the Harijans to fight the British with your spirit of Non-violence. In this struggle, we lost some of our fellow Harijans.

Karna: *Masterji*, basically Lavya is rebel. Since he adhered to your call of Non-violence. . . he had to lose some his clan members in the hands of cruel British. . .

Krishnaji: Is it? Good. Keep it. . .

Lavya: (*politely*): Krishnaji. . . Our fight is in duel way. . . the both ways are to get freedom. We fight British for independence. We fight the higher caste people for emancipation. . . The atrocities of higher caste people on the Harijans are enormous. Please make us free from the humiliations even after independence.

Krishnaji: (*pretends love*): Be cool, my friends. I heard some of the atrocities on Harijans in this village. That is the reason why I've come here to solve the problem. Everyone is equal on this earth. . . There should be no harassment, no humiliations, no caste discrimination. . .

Lavya: Teach a lesson to the higher caste. . . Krishnaji, we have respect in your words. Teach them to stop the harassment, humiliations on the Harijans. If the harassment continues even after your teaching, I swear my hatchet would taste the blood of the higher caste people.

Krishnaji: Lavya! No. . . Don't be aggressive. . . I've come here to solve the problems. (*Krishnajiji goes to the group of higher caste. The group of untouchables sits silently*)

Dharma: What happened, Krishnaji? What did the stray untouchables say?

Krishnaji: (*passively*): Don't shout aloud. . . Maintain patience. Pay heed to my words . . . Don't provoke the untouchables. It is the need of the hour to behave like a fox. We have to work along with untouchables. . .

Bheem: (*fulmination*): With untouchables?

Krishnaji: Act! Pretend! As if you're mingled with untouchables for a few years. We are going to get independence . . . independence forever . . . mastery over untouchables forever. . .

Arjun: Then. . . The untouchables also get independence?

Krishnaji: Independence is only for the higher caste from the brutal control of the British. As the might is right. . . We would rule this country forever after independence. The untouchables will become slaves and social

lepers forever. Their situation would be worse than the situation they have today. Wait patiently till freedom is given.

Dharma: (*disgustingly*): It would be very crestfallen embarrassment for the higher caste people to work with Harijans. . . I don't like it. Let us fight separately.

Krishnaji: My rigid aim is to see the untouchables under our iron feet . . . If we free Harijans now, they will join the British group. The British treat them on a par with us. A little change is happening in the lives of untouchables these days. We have foiled the effort of British to do good. They allowed the untouchables into Churches. They wanted to give religious, social, economical freedom to them. . . If it continues to be so, British will give them the political freedom also. We will become slaves, and paupers. . . You know. . . this freedom struggle is a duel game to extend our hegemony. Freedom Struggle is to expel British, and to make Harijans untouchables forever. If the British dwell for a long time, there would be no caste system in Hindia. Hence, we have to expel British first. Their Bible says, everyone, either poor or rich, is equal. If the lessons of the Bible penetrate into the minds of the Harijans, the dominant group of Harijans will become powerful and rule over us.

Bheem: (*gleefully*): O God! How thought provoking Krishnaji is!

Nakul: I and Saha guessed the intention of Krishnaji. . . very in advance.

Arjun: Lunatics! You should have informed us to make us tension free. . .

Krishnaji: It is not the time to discuss whether they know my intention or not. . Hey! Pretend friendship with untouchables. . . Don't be aggressive. Let us go to the cattle of untouchables. . .

(Krishnajiji paces and stands amidst the two groups. He beckons Dharma, Bheem, Arjun, Nakul, and Saha. He also beckons Lavya, Karna, and Suodan. Arjun brings a chair. Krishnajiji sits. The both groups stand in opposite direction.)

Krishnaji: Hey! My friends! I am very sad to sit amidst you. . . that too to solve conflicts between you. The first thing I suggest is 'Be United'. We have to maintain unity in diversity. You have to cooperate with each other to be uncooperative with British. Don't create violence because I am fighting the British with the weapon of non-violence. But some freedom fighters are violent. We are all one. . .

Suodan: Krishnaji! The violent Lavya turned to be non-violent because of your call of non-violence.

Karna: Hey! Suodan! Tell about the civil disobedience that we followed. . .

Lavya: (*turns towards the Suodan, and Karna*): Hey! Stop your filthy boasting. . . (*stands before Krishnajiji with aggressive mood*) Krishnaji! No doubt. . . we are fighting for the freedom. But more we fight for the freedom, more we faced caste discrimination, humiliations, and harassments. . . I reiterate. . .if the humiliation on us continues. . . we turn to be non-violent again. . .

Suodan: (*rigidly*): Yes! True! Krishnaji! We have been treated as untouchables by the higher caste people.

Krishnaji: (*pretends love and innocence*): Untouchables? I already gave a call to abandon and root out the untouchability from our country. Untouchability is crime. Forget everything and fight with unity.

Razole Prabhakar / The Vain Sacrifice Of Dalit Patriots: One Act Play

Lavya: To be united, caste discrimination should be eradicated. If the eradication of caste is not possible, there would be no meaning for the fight for freedom.

Krishnaji: (*caresses the head of Lavya*): I tell you that if the untouchability continues even after independence, the situation of untouchables would be worse than they lived under Colonial rule. I don't like this untouchability in this village. (*looks at Dharma*)

(*Dharma comes mildly forward and stands before Krishnaji*)

Dharma: I've been heading this village for a long time. There were no such situations in this village, master.

Lavya: (*seriously*): Krishnaji! Dharma's justice is biased. Can higher caste people rape the untouchables. . . can kill. . . humiliate? Dalit should abide by the word of Dharma? (*Looks at Krishnaji*) Krishnaji! Dharma pronounced and imposed a dogma on untouchables. Do you know? How cruel? How silly the dogma is? It is that if Dalit women are seduced and molested, it is the rape and molestation done by the God. How inhuman the dogma is? Are we social, religious, and economic slaves?

Bheem: Yes! What Dharma said is right. The untouchables are slaves. Their duty is to please the higher caste people by all means. . .

Krishnaji: No. . . The dogma imposed on the Harijan clan is inhuman.

Karna: (*complains*): Krishnaji! I bring to your kind notice that once a higher caste woman flirted with Suodan. There was no mistake of him, but he was tonsured and was removed moustaches. . . How humiliation it is? The higher caste people can rape the Harijan woman, but we should not look at higher caste woman by chance?

Krishnaji: (*looks at Arjun*): Arjun! What do you say?

Arjun: We follow your foot prints and words, master. We will behave as you say. Order. . . my master. . . We remove the dogma from today onwards.

Krishnaji: Hey! My friends! Pay attention to my words! Untouchability is crime. We are all equals. Fight British with one voice. Be united! Swaraj is at hand. We will have our won administration soon. . . (*looks at Arjun*) Arjun! Bring your group to me! (*looks at Lavya*) Lavya ! Bring your Harijan group to me! (*the two groups have come to Krishnaji*) Let us all be patriotic. Let us fight together. (*All stretched their hands*) Say after me! 'I fight for freedom of our country till my last breath. We shall maintain unity in diversity. I adhere to non-violence and Civil Disobedience'. Lavya, shake the hand of Dharma. (*Lavya shakes the hand of Dharma*).

Lavya: *Jai Bolo. . . Krishnajibiki. . . (pause) Jai Bolo . . . Krishnajibiki. . .* (the entire Dalit group shouts 'Jai').

Krishnaji: (*lovingly keeps hand on the shoulder of Lavya*): I know your commitment and dedication in freedom struggle. Keep it up. Maintain amity with other caste people also.

Lavya: Okay Ji.

Krishnaji: (*waves his hand at the Untouchables*): Hey! Friends! Keep this momentum and spirit on. . . I promise you that there would be no caste humiliations. (*Looks at Lavya*) Okay! Lavya, ignite patriotism in the drab

Razole Prabhakar / The Vain Sacrifice Of Dalit Patriots: One Act Play

minds of your clan. It is your responsibility to make them patriots. Right. . . I take leave from you. I've to attend another meeting. Bye. .

Lavya: Bye. . . Ji. We wish you all the success. . .

Krishnaji: Dharma, Arjun, and Bheem will give me send off. Lavya! You can stay back.

Lavya: Okay, Krishnaji. . .

(Dharma, Bheem, Arjun, Nakul, and Saha accompany Krishnaji. They go little away from the untouchables)

Krishnaji: Don't think otherwise. My dear higher caste true freedom fighters, I was forced to speak in favor of the Harijans because Maharkar already started to group together all the Harijans. Harijans under his leadership started to rebel against the Hindu Varna system. It is the need of pretention like the friends of Harijans at least till we get freedom from the British. Pretend to be in close affinity with Harijans. But . . . see that they must be under our iron feet forever. . . If we free them they will join the British group. The British already treated them on a par with us. They allowed the untouchables into Churches. They wanted to give religious, social, economical freedom to them. . . If it continues to be so, British will give them the political freedom also.

Arjun: What an outstanding foresight you have! Krishnaji. . .

Bheem: *(claps)*: Well said. . . Well said. . .

Dharma: Let us follow the excellent strategy of Krishnaji.

Saha: Krishnaji, I sense a bad omen today!

Krishnaji: Yes! This place may replete with blood today. My dear higher caste people! I've the information that British Kristee, British Military Officer, is coming with his British Hindian Army force to foil the meeting. He's aggressive, merciless, and monstrous. Let the Harijans have meeting, but the higher caste people should not participate in the meeting. Arjun. . .! If possible, exploit this opportunity to your advantage. Be careful! Be careful! I take leave from you. . . .Bye. . .

Dharma: *(shouts)*: Praise. . . the glory of Krishnaji. . . Praise. . . the leadership of Krishnaji. . . *(all shout after Dharma, as Krishnaji departs from the stage). (the five members come to the group of untouchables).*

Arjun: Hello! Lavya, and my dear Harijans, Let us fight together for our freedom and self-government. We are all one.

Dharma: Okay! Karna, Suodan, and Lavya! It gives us immense pleasure to work along with you for the right cause.

Bheem: Lavya! You convene a meeting with your clan today. . . We will convene meeting with our clan tomorrow. *(turns towards the higher caste clan and announces)* My dear higher caste people go home today. . . We will have our meeting tomorrow.

Karna: Bheem! What did you say? Why should you convene meetings separately? Let us have a meeting together.

Razole Prabhakar / The Vain Sacrifice Of Dalit Patriots: One Act Play

Lavya: (*advising*): Karna! Let them have their own freedom. . . Krishnaji will look after everything. Let us give freedom to them to convene their meeting tomorrow. . .

All the five: Thank you, Lavya. . . We will meet you tomorrow. . . . (*All the five and the higher caste people leave the stage*).

Lavya: (*sonorously addresses*): My dear clan, we are no more untouchables. . . Krishnaji promised us that. It is the peak time for us to fight for our self-government. Let us lead our struggle in the way of non-violence, and civil disobedience. . . If the struggle demands our lives, let us give up for the right cause, and let us make ourselves martyrs. . . . My dear friends! We should adhere to the advice of Krishnaji. The untouchability will be eradicated after we get independence. We should fight untidily along with the higher caste people. *Jai Bolo*. . . *Krishnajijiki*. . . .(pause) *Jai Bolo*. . . *Krishnajijiki*. . . (*the entire Dalit group shouts 'Jai' after Lavya*).

Suodan: (*gazes perplexingly at right side of the stage, and beholds*): Hey! Lavya! Pay heed to the loud and deep-toned voices. I hope it is the ugly voice of Kristee. He may be coming here with his British Hindian Army police to foil our meeting.

Lavya: (*addresses the untouchables*): My dear friends, I sense danger . . . You're all advised to leave this place. . . go home safely. . . I, Suodan, and Karna, will negotiate with Kristee. . . (*All the people leave the stage*).

(*Kristee with along with Narasimha, and an escort of Kristee, enters the stage. Narasimha stands behind Kristee. Narasimha is a staunch supporter of Varna System. He believes that untouchables are inferiors*).

Kristee: (*wrathfully*): My dear colonized slaves! How dare you to convene a meeting to rebel against your master who tries to civilize the barbarous mass. . .

Lavya: (*widens his shaggy bosom*): We crave for freedom . . .

Kristee: Freedom!

Karna: Yes! Freedom from your tyranny, brutality. . .

Kristee: Yes! Well. . . We try to give freedom to all the down trodden people. Hence, we allow untouchables also into churches. . . we tried to establish educational institutions for the development of untouchables. . . But you have foolishly demolished them.

Lavya: (*aggressively forges*): How ironical it is? You. . . alien beasts have come with scriptures in your hands. We respected you because our scriptures say '*Athidi Devobhava*'. At last, you made us slaves, grabbed our land, and kept your filthy scriptures in our hands. . .

Kristee: *Ha .hahaha*. . . Hey! Even before the advent of British, your lands were in the hands of bourgeois, landlords. . . Had we taken your land? (pause) Where was your land? (pause). We have seized only the land of landlords to lay railroads, and to distribute the land among the untouchables. We tried to establish social justice and tried to develop commerece in your country. . .

Lavya: Is killing the innocent natives' development . . . ?

Razole Prabhakar / The Vain Sacrifice Of Dalit Patriots: One Act Play

Kristee: No. . . . We wanted to create social awareness. . . We tried to mitigate the economical disparities between haves and have nots by encouraging the untouchables social, economically, and religiously. We treated you on a par with higher caste people. But the Hindu varna system did not permit us so. . . We tried to eradicate Child Marriages, Sathi Sahagamana . . .

Karna: You're trying to deceive us with your cryptic and mystical words. . .

Kristee: Unless you realize yourselves and fight for your rights. . . nobody can rescue you.

Suodan: (*with an innocent face*): Krishnaji promised us that untouchability would be eradicated after independence.

Kristee: (*wittily*): Fools! Your fate seems to be on a downward trajectory. You. . . Ha. . . ha. . . scapegoats. . . Firstly you get freedom from the bondage of Hindu Varna system, and secondly fight for the freedom of the nation. You're unable to understand the foxy nature of Krishnaji. . . If you blindly believe Krishnaji, your situation would be worse than today. To believe in civil disobedience is to believe in anarchy. The Non cooperation movement launched by Krishnaji is to get Swaraj for the higher castes, and the Civil disobedience is to establish their Ram raj.

Lavya: Don't scold Krishnaji. . .

Kristee: Illiterate goats! You're prisoners in the Krishnaji's trick. . . Did you have freedom in the past . . . ?

Lavya: No. . . (*pause*) (*mildly*) We were like slaves. . .

Kristee: Who were the masters to you?

Lavya: All the people of higher strata. . .

Kristee: Did they allow you into temples?

Suodan: No. . .

Kristee: But. . . we allowed you . . . because everyone is equal . . . according to the Bible. . . See. . . the false intention of Krishnaji is to make you untouchables forever. . .

Lavya: (*perplexingly*): Forever? How?

Kristee: The higher social people enjoyed power over you. They don't want to lose the domination over untouchables. . .

Lavya: Kristee. You're trying to poison my mind with your filthy words. . .

Karna: Kristee. . . you can't change our rigid minds. . .

Kristee: (*submissively*): Let me tell you, my friends. . . Krishnaji and his group wanted to foil your progress. As such they encouraged you to demolish the churches and schools constructed by British. . . Anti imperial movement by subaltern? The freedom fight of the Dalits? It is to protect the needs of the elite group who try to continue dominance over the untouchables. They don't want to treat untouchables social equals.

Razole Prabhakar / The Vain Sacrifice Of Dalit Patriots: One Act Play

Lavya: As part of Non-cooperation, and Civil Disobedience calls given by Krishnaji, we rejected the foreign goods. . . demolished the churches and schools built by British. . .

Kristee: What sort of foreign goods you used?

Suodan: We are very poor . . . how can you use the costly foreign goods?

Kristee: While you starve, what kind of promise do you find in rejecting the foreign goods . . .? In fact, that movement is not for the freedom of untouchables, but for the freedom of landlords for getting their lands back, and to show bossism over the untouchables. . . Bossism forever. . . Bossism forever. . .

Lavya: You're trying to divide us. (*sarcastically*) *Ha..ha..ha..ha* . . . your policy is 'divide and rule'. . . you have succeeded in the past with it. . . Now. . . again. . .you're employing your trick. . .

Kristee: Your society was already divided into Varnas. Who am I to divide you? Instead of wasting your time under foxy cause of freedom fighting under the pseudo-freedom fighters. . . You fight for your social, economical, religious freedom, and fight against the inhuman, perilous Varna System. . . Instead of deifying Krishnaji, deify the real fighter, Maharkar.

Lavya: (*inquisitively*): Maharkar?

Suodan: Who is he?

Kristee: A real fighter against the varna system. . . He's the true patriot who fights for the freedom for untouchables. We favored Maharkar's move to get separate identity for untouchables. But. . . Your so called freedom fighter, Krishnaji, went for hunger strike against giving separate identity for untouchables. . .

Lavya: (*innocently*): Why?

Kristee: Because, Maybe, he wanted to keep untouchables under the yoke of slavery forever. . . If untouchables are freed from political bondage, that leads them towards social, and economical equality. The Hindu Varna System doesn't support equality. . .

Karna: But Krishnaji... proclaimed that no one will be treated as untouchable by reason of birth. All the rights will be given to untouchables in social institutions as given to higher caste people.

Kristee: *Ha. . .ha. . .* Did you have marital relation with higher caste people to establish social equality?

Karna: No. . . never. . .

Kristee: Unless the inter-caste marriages are performed, no social equality is possible. Ask your Krishnaji to perform inter-caste marriages. . . Anyway, I admire Maharkar, a visionary, a man with complete social outlook. He's the symbol of love of Christ. My dear people! Contemplate . . . follow your true leader, Maharkar.

Lavya: (*orders Suodan, and Karna*): Say! Maharkarki zindabad. . . Maharkarki. . .

Suodan &

Razole Prabhakar / The Vain Sacrifice Of Dalit Patriots: One Act Play

Karna : *Zindabad* . .

Lavya: Let us go and support Maharkar. . .

(All start to move off the stage. All of sudden, furious Narasimha stabs Kristee. . . Lavya, Suodan, and Karna attempt foil the murder of Kristee, but in vain. Narasimha runs away shouting 'Varna System long live... Long live Varna System.)

Suodan: *(surprisingly checks the pulse of Kristee and touches the nostrils)*: Lavya. . . It seems Kristee is dead. . .

Karna: *(fearfully)*: What can we do now?

Lavya: Let us take him to the local doctor . . . hurry up . . . hurry up. . . *(they try to lift him up)*

Karna: Lavya! He's dead! *(pause)*

Lavya: *(contemplates)*: Dead. . .! Karna and Suodan! I sense danger. I can boldly face the danger, but you leave this place. If I die in the hands of these wicked people, lead our broken men and keep up the uprising against varna system. I am ready to shower my blood. Let my boiling blood that touches the earth beget myriad martyrs from Untouchables. Let my blood erupt terrible beauty in the hearts of the Untouchables.

Suodan: No. . . We won't leave. . . let us face the danger together.

Karna: Yes! You're the leader of untouchables . . . let us fight together. . .

Lavya: *(yells)*: I order in the name of our ancestors. Please leave this place for our untouchables' sake.

(Suodan, and Karna leave. Dharma, Bheem, Arjun, Nakul, Saha, and Narasimha enter. They come roaring, and shouting 'Kristee is killed by Lavya. . . Kristee is killed by Lavya. . .)

Dharma: Catch hold of these untouchables. They killed Kristee. . .

Lavya: *(looks seriously at Narasimha, takes out hatchet from his waist, and tries to chase Narasimha)*: Ye! Bastard! You have played a trick. You have killed Kristee. . . and now pretending as if you're an innocent. . .

Narasimha: Help! Help me! Save me from Lavya's wrath. . . *(Nobody has come to protect him)* Dharma! Save me! I acted upon your advice. But now you're mute . . . Lavya! Please. . . I beg you . . . leave me. . .

(Lavya cuts the head of Narasimha very angrily. None tried to stop Lavya. Meanwhile, Peter, British Military Officer along with police force, enters.)

Peter: *(comes hazily, cries on the dead body of Kristee, and looks angrily at Lavya whose hands are drenched with blood)*: You . . . Untouchable! Why did you kill Kristee?

Lavya: *(perplexingly)*: No. . . I did not kill, but Narasimha. . .

Dharma: No. . . Mr. Peter. He's lying. . . I and all my friends saw. Lavya killed Kristee.

Razole Prabhakar / The Vain Sacrifice Of Dalit Patriots: One Act Play

Nakul: Sir, Lavya killed not only Kristee, but also Narasimha, a British Hindian soldier.

Bheem: Yes. Yes. Lavya killed Kristee.

Arjun: Mr. Peter, Lavya is a liar. . .

Saha: It's true. It's true Mr. Peter.

Peter: (*aggressively*): Untouchables! How poisonous and perilous you're! We tried to teach civilization to you. It's true your disposition is barbarity, cruelty. You deserved stringent punishment. (*wrathfully orders the cops*) Arrest! Arrest! This beast. (*roars*) Arrest him. . . (*Dharma, Bheem, Arjun, Nakul, and Saha huddle up with fear because of the grave roar of Peter*).

Lavya: (*angrily moves forward*): Stop! Stop! Peter! You seem to be irrational. Fathom out the truth. . . I did not kill Kristee, but I killed Narasimha. . . because Narasimha killed Kristee. . . It's a premeditated intrigue of these officious fools. . . (*looks at Dharma, Bheem, Arjun, Nakul, Saha, and spits on their faces*) Foxes. . . Are you freedom fighters? Are you patriots? Are you the people who amalgamate with untouchables after independence? (*spits*).

Peter: Stop! Stop shouting!

Dharma: (*pretending fear*): Sir, He will kill us. Please arrest him. . .

Peter: (*roars*): Arrest him. . .

Lavya: (*roars with hatchet in his hand*): Arrest! Let your police come to me. . . This hatchet will taste the blood of your police. . . Peter! Alien Beast! Who are you to arrest me?

(*While Lavya faces at the police, Arjun hurls a big stone that hurts the forehead of Lavya. Lavya becomes little unconscious. The police arrest Lavya. Little later, he is conscious*).

Peter: Beat this beast! Beat this beast! (*Police beat him severely*)

Police: Master, he is unconscious again. . .

Peter: Tonsure! Tonsure! Shave moustache! Moustache . . . (*sarcastically*): Are you a hero? If so, protect yourselves!

(*Dharma, Bheem, Arjun, Nakul, and Saha gleefully execute the tonsure to Lavya. They spit on the face of Lavya*).

Peter: I order! The Army of British Hindian police! Drag this beast, Lavya unto the city and prison him. . . (*Police drag the body of Lavya off the stage*).

Scene II

(Scene is after a couple of years, on 14 August, 1947 at 11.45. pm. Lavya comes out of prison. The scene takes place in front of Prison).

Peter: We are giving freedom to your country. . . As such . . . we decided to give freedom to you. . .

Lavya: (*gleefully and jubilantly*): Freedom! O my God! Promise dawns in the lives of Untouchables. . . There would be no starvation . . . there would be social, political, and economic disparities. . . There would be no humiliations, and harassment to untouchables. . .

Peter: Don't be over ambitious . . .Lavya. . . The Untouchables situation is going to be worse than the situation under colonial rule. . .

Lavya: Sir, Please. . . Don't provoke me again. . . (*looks at Suodan coming sadly to Lavya*) Hey! Suodan. . . How are you? How is Karna? How is our sibling? You know. . . (pause) We are going to get freedom. . . Don't be sad . . . be jubilant. . . (*looks hither and thither*) Where is Karna? (pause)

Suodan: (*weeps*): O God!

Lavya: What happened?

Suodan: (*weeps*): How shall I say? Karna was brutally killed by Arjun a couple of weeks back.

Lavya: (*sadly*): Why? What is the reason?

Suodan: (*weeps*): Karna's wife was raped and killed by Arjun. . . He went all alone to retaliate against Arjun. The wild beasts mercilessly killed Karna. (*grimly*) I don't know. . .when our men are not untouchable, how our women are touchable?

Lavya: (*aggressively*): How inhuman it is!

Suodan: Moreover . . .they poisoned the rivulet. Our people drunk and died. Further. . .

Lavya: (*sadly*): Further. . .?

Suodan: (*hits his forehead*): What they consider you Traitor. . .

Lavya: Yah. . . Traitor who killed Hindian Narasimha.

Lavya: (*roars with uncontrollable pain*): What can we do . . .? Let us unite and rebel?

Suodan: (*in choking voice*): Today, our situation is worse than yesterday. . . We can't avenge. Krishnaji has been deifying as the national leader. . . Dharma, Bheem, Arjun, Nakul, and Saha have been recognized as great freedom fighters. . . They have great following today. . . We can't do anything against them. . . Political power is transformed from the British to the first three strata of Hindu society. They got power to rule the fourth varna. The Untouchables have become slaves under the four varnas.

Razole Prabhakar / The Vain Sacrifice Of Dalit Patriots: One Act Play

Lavya: (*looks up*): There are multi-colours of exploded firework in the sky. . .

Suodan: (sadly): O! God! It is 12.00 pm. Hindia got freedom. . . (*sadly*) Hindia got freedom. . .

Lavya: O God! What sort of sin our clan did? Why did You make us untouchables? Why did You give us flesh and blood? How can we face the slaughter of the higher caste people and live? Freedom . . . Freedom has begotten the perpetual slavery. Perpetual untouchability. . . (*with the uncontrollable pain, Lavya falls down unconsciously*).

Suodan: (*yells madly and sits abruptly beside the motionless body of Lavya*): My firend! My friend! A true Dalit Patriot! What happened to you. . . What happened to you. . . . Has your dedication and sacrifice gone in vain. . . in vain. . . !? (*looks at sky and stretches his hands*): O my God! Hindia got freedom. . . Untouchables lost freedom. . . Hindia got freedom. . . Untouchables lost freedom. . . (*yells deeply*) Hindia got freedom. . . Untouchables lost freedom. . .